

Application of Management Theories, Decision Making Techniques and Effective Conflict Resolutions in Tertiary Educational Institutions Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the application of management theory, decision-making technique and effective conflict resolutions in tertiary educational institution Kebbi state Nigeria. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design of correlation type, and the population of this study comprise of 2963 participants, the Lecturers and management staff of the tertiary educational institution in Kebbi State. The study used Research Advisors, (2006) table for determining sample size for the Lecturers and management staff and 333 was realized. Three sets of instruments were used for the data collection from the lecturers and management staff of the colleges of education under study and one of these instruments was adapted from Manga, (2022) titled: Application of Management Theories Questionnaire (AMTQ), while the other questionnaire titled: Application of Decision-Making Techniques Questionnaire (ADMTQ) and Effective Conflicts Resolution Questionnaire (ECRQ) respectively. All the three set of instruments were handed over to the team of experts in educational management for validation and after these experts have done a thorough examination of these instrument, their observation made the instrument valid for the study. The reliability of the instrument was obtained by using the test re-test method, also the reliability index of 0.93, 0.83 and 0.811 respectively were obtained which made the instruments reliable. The researchers and the trained research assistants personally administer these questionnaires to the respondent in their offices of various institution during working hours. The researchers employed the descriptive and inferential statistics for the data analysis. Mean score was used to analyze the research question. The person moment product coefficient was used to analysed the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance regression analysis method was used among the three variables with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 20.0

Keywords: Management Theories, Decision, Decision Making, Techniques, Conflict Resolution, Tertiary Institution.

Introduction

Management theories as well as decision making in an educational setting is crucial, essential and a very needful resource. Therefore, how educational managers are applying this will be of paramount importance to the activities of educational sector like the ministries of education and educational institutions performances. How educational managers are applying and utilizing their passé on this will have an incredible result on not only their thoughts, feelings and job quality alone but to the entire organisation Block and Grondin, (2014). It is in this regards the researchers envisage management theory as a tool used to develop the individual so that he becomes useful to himself, his family and the society generally.

Therefore, the intended goals of education to be achieved by the tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria are clearly stated in the national policy education which divided education into four levels which are the pre-primary, primary and lower secondary education, upper secondary and higher/tertiary education. Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) & Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). In all these, tertiary educational institutions make the optimum contribution to national

development. The tertiary educational institution makes professional course content reflect national requirements, intensify and diversify its programmes for the development of high-level manpower within the context of the needs of the state, makes entrepreneurial skills acquisition a requirement for all Nigerian tertiary institution and makes all students to be part of a general programme for all-round improvement (Federal Republic Nigeria, 2013).

The importance of decision-making in management are numerous whatever a manager does he does through making decisions. Moreover, the organizations that did excel in decision-making and turned out on top after the survey had better performances and better financial conditions some of its importance are: saves time and money, boosts productivity, better use of resources, efficient costing, identifying the right opportunities, helps establishing achievable goals, coming up with new products and services, hiring the best people, better marketing strategies and also very important in conflict prevention.

While in terms of effective conflicts resolutions, first of all Conflict is when two or more values, perspectives and opinions are contradictory in nature and have not been aligned or agreed to including: within oneself when one is not living according to one's values; when values and perspectives are threatened; or discomfort from fear of the unknown or from lack of fulfillment. Conflict is inevitable and often good, for example, good teams always go through a "form, storm, norm and perform" period. Getting the most out of diversity means contradictory values, perspectives and opinions McNamara, (2007). Many people view conflict as an activity that is almost totally negative and has no redeeming qualities. Some consider it as dysfunctional, destructive, and the same time as a catalyst for change, creativity and production Posigha&Oghuvwu, (2009). The colleges of educations in North Western region of the country like any other organization are not immune from conflict. This is because; in any circumstances where two or more people co-exist to form an organization, conflict is anticipated, it is always inevitable.

There are effective and ineffective conflicts, "A conflict is said to be effective when it is constructively discussed by the parties and amicable terms for settlement reached". Constructively managed conflict induces a positive performance while poorly managed conflict heated up the environment to bring about dislocation of the entire group and polarization, reduced productivity on job performance, psychological and physical injury, emotional distress and inability to sleep, interference with problem activities, escalation of differences into antagonistic position and malice and increased hostility (Albert & Yahaya, 2013).

Theoretical Framework

This paper hinges on Kuntz's Contingency Theory in Manga (2015). The Contingency theory emphasis administrator's ability to use a combination of approaches to meet particular circumstances and constraints an organisation may encounter. The administrator responds to peculiar circumstances within a situation before taking a step in tackling issues. Under this theory there is no one best approach to any issue. The particular circumstance of a specific situation determines the best choice or decision. Applying a Contingency approach requires that administrator diagnoses a given situation and applies appropriate measures to address the present condition. This theory is related to the current study in a manner that it gives the educational managers the choice of which type of management theory or decision-making techniques to use in resolving conflicts in the tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria and fills the gap of the non-applicability of management theories and decision-making techniques by the educational managers of the tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Galani, & Galanakis, (2022). Conducted research on "A Systematic Literature Review on organizational Psychology on the Rise of McGregor's X and Y Theory: According to this theory, motivation can and should be achieved in different ways based on whether the employee is categorized as type x or type y according to McGregor. The paper, review was conducted in order to address the contribution and current findings of the theory in the modern workplace was found out that there is low and non-active involvement of putting into practice this theory of X and Y. A number of recent studies were identified and concluded with ambiguous findings which later on lead to other studies in constructing a valid scale for evaluating X and Y attitudes-behaviours and job performance.

Adeyemi and Ademilun (2012), conducted research on conflict management strategies and administrative effectiveness in Nigeria Universities. The study used a population on 62 Universities in Nigeria in 2010. A sample of 12 Universities was used for the study; the statistical instrument used to analysis the data was Regression Analysis of variance. The study revealed that the occurrence of conflict in Nigerian Universities was at a frequent level, foremost among these was the one between the academic staff and the University management. The finding of study highlighted that communication gap between management and workers were leading cause of conflict in the Universities. The study recommended that the management of universities in Nigeria should adopt a blend of management strategies in managing conflicts in their institutions for higher labour dispute resolution. The two studies shared the same similarities dependent variable but differed in population and level of education, the previous study was on universities only while the current was on

tertiary educational institution at all level not only the university but including other higher educational institute of learning in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Problem of the Study

There are numerous problems in the tertiary educational institution in the state especially here in the north west zone, Nigeria that are currently destabilizing the survival of peaceful educational atmosphere, especially the issue of lacking the technical know-how on the application of management theory and Decision-making techniques. One of this problem bedeviling the tertiary educational institution in Kebbi State is for example the wrong application of McGregor theory X and Y theory of management theory in the tertiary educational institution in Kebbi state in Nigeria. The theory X is of the opinion that humans naturally hate work, while the theory Y is of the opinion that humans naturally love work, but one basic fundamental problem here that is a problem to the tertiary educational institution, more so, is the issue of indigeneship factor, this is the main reason why lecturers don't like working and give their best as it supposed to, because they claim that being indigenes of the state, work should not be a do or die affair after all the management cannot take action on the lecturers because the employee who are the lecturers will quickly run to the politicians who negotiated for their employment since the tertiary educational institution is owned by the state government.

Ethnicity also plays a major role in the 'board politics' and is another major socio-cultural issue/problem affecting the tertiary educational institution. Merit in this case has to give way to ethnicity and this is associated with intra-group conflicts may occur due to disagreement or differences among group members or sub-groups regarding the goals, functions or activities of the group. there may be inter-group conflicts which tend to develop when there is 'us against them' for example, in departments or levels of decision making. Hence, groups see each other as enemies and tend to become hostile; in-turn, positive relationship decrease. Interpersonal issues in the tertiary educational institution is another problem it occurs due to: 1) Differing work roles and work load, 2) Individual differences on values, goals and needs, and 3) Individuals competing for resources, such as, promotions or work assignment. There are different strategies and methods suggested by the literature to manage the conflicts in the schools. An educational institution is a heterogeneous assembly of youths and adults from different family, cultural, religious, ethnic and socio-economic backgrounds.

Objectives of the study

The objective of the study is to:

1. find out the extent application of management theories in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State
2. find out the extent of application of decision-making techniques in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State
3. find out the level of effective conflict resolution in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State

Research Questions

The study provided answers to the following research questions:

1. what is the extent of application of management theory in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State
2. what is the extent of application of decision-making techniques in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State
3. what is the level of effectiveness of conflict resolutions in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State

Research Null Hypothesis

Based on the research objectives the research null Hypothesis was formulated:

1. There is no significant relationship between the application of management theories and level of effective conflict resolution in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State
2. There is no significant relationship between the application of decision-making techniques and level of effective conflict resolution in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State
3. There is no significant relationship among Applications of management theories decision-making techniques and the level of effective conflict resolutions in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive research design the correlational type. The population of the study was 2,963 participants comprises of all the lecturers and management staff of the tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. 333 Sample size was drawn from the population by the use of Research Advisor (2006). The researchers used the purposive sampling to select all tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria because they are the target population of interest to the researchers of this study. The staff were stratified as lecturers and management staff, while proportionate sampling was used to determine the sample size that was drawn from each stratum and institution. The study applied the proportionate sampling technique to determine the number of participants that has been drawn from each school to ensure equitable representation of the population from each institution. Random sampling was used to

select participants from within each institution. The random sampling gave equal opportunity to all subjects selected that formed part of the sample which enable the generalization of the findings without being biased.

The study utilized three structured questionnaires as the instrument for collecting data. The first instrument was titled: "Application of Management Theory Questionnaire" (AMTQ) which was served as the instrument for collecting data in tertiary educational institutions. The AMTQ was adapted from that of Manga (2023) to suit the peculiarity of the study. The AMTQ was structured on a 5-point Likert's scale model ranging from 1 point = Very Low Extent (VLE); 2 points = Low Extent (LE); 3 points = Moderate Extent (ME); 4 points = High Extent (HE); and 5 points = Very High Extent (VHE). The mean score of 3.00 points will be used as cut-off for satisfactory extent of management theory x and y while below 3.00 mean was used as unsatisfactory extent of management theory in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

The second instrument was a self-designed questionnaire titled: application of decision-making questionnaire (ADMQ) was used to collect data on management decision on various techniques used in tertiary educational institution in Kebbi State, Nigeria. The questionnaire has item statements. The questionnaire was structured in such a way that it will request the participant to tick relevant option from the five (5) Likert scale as follows; Very High Extent (VHE) 5 points, High Extent (HE); 4 points, Moderate Extent (ME); 3 points Lower Extent (LE); 2 points, Very Low Extent (VLE) 1 point This have required the respondents to rate extent at which each of the listed items have effect on the standard of tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

The Effective Conflict Resolution Questionnaire (ECRQ) was adapted from Manga (2017) which was used to collect data on effective conflict resolutions in tertiary educational institutions.

The ECRQ consists of 12 items and the researcher modified the ECRQ making the number of items to 10 items to enable the restructured of the statement suit the study. The instrument was structured on a 5-point Likert's scale model ranging from 1 point = Very Low Level (VLL); 2 points = Low Level (LL); 3 points = Moderate Level (ML); 4 points = High Level (HL); and 5 points = Very High Level (VHL). The mean score is also of 3.00 points and above on the scale of 5.0 was used as cut-off for satisfactory Extent of effective conflict resolution while below 3.00 points is unsatisfactory extent of effective conflict resolution.

The content validity of AMTQ was determined by revalidating the instrument by experts in the fields of educational management. The content validity of ECRQ was determined by revalidating the adapted instrument. and the reliability index of the instrument Application of Management Theories Questionnaire (AMTQ) is $r = 0.912$, the second instrument Application of Decision-Making Techniques Questionnaire (ADMTQ) is $r = 0.831$ and while the third instrument Effective Conflict Resolution Questionnaire (ECRQ) is $r = 0.811$ respectively. which have made the research instruments reliable in measuring the variables for this study.

Descriptive and inferential statistics was used for data analysis. The researchers used frequency, percentage and mean in analyzing the data in response to the descriptive research questions via Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 20.0 data analysis software. The hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at 0.05 level of significance to correlate management theories and decision-making techniques in effective conflict resolution in tertiary educational institutions as well as regression analysis was used among the three variables in the study.

Results

Three questions were answered and three null Hypothesis was tested and presented in table 1 to 6.

Research Question One:

RQ1: What is the extent of the application of management theories in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. The research question was answered and presented in table 1. The responses on the application of management theories in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. is presented in the table 1.

Table 1: Extent of the Application Management Theories in Tertiary Educational Institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	Std Dev.	Decision
1	School administrator provide an enabling environment to motivate Lecturers to like their job	2.74	.538	LE
2	Lecturers are given sufficient autonomy to be self-directing in their activities	2.57	.768	LE
3	Lecturers are adequately controlled by their supervisors to ensure compliance with directives	2.89	.446	LE
4	Lecturers who are negligent of their duties are reasonably punished as a deterrent to others	2.22	.682	LE
5	Lecturers are given additional responsibilities in addition to their teaching, research and community service	3.49	.897	ME
6	Lecturers are adequately rewarded for their commitment to duty through exceptional performance	2.66	.801	LE
7	Lecturers are given facilities for recreation and relaxation so as to reduce their mental stress resulting from the complex activities of their office	2.17	.735	LE
Weighted Mean (\bar{x})		2.68	0.16	LE

Source: Field Work (2023)

N=333, Cut off Mean=3.00

KEY

VHE = very high extent, HE = high extent, ME = moderate extent, LE = low extent, VLE = very low extent

A look at Table 1, indicates extent of the application of Management in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. A look at the item on lecturers are given additional responsibilities in addition to their teaching, research and community service (Mean = 3.49) is the only one that satisfied the threshold and thereby was considered as effective in the extent of application of McGregor's theory in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

But the table indicates that items on school administrator provide an enabling environment to motivate lecturers to like their job (Mean = 2.74), lecturers are given sufficient autonomy to be self-directing in their activities (Mean = 2.57), lecturers are adequately controlled by their supervisors to ensure compliance with directives (Mean = 2.89), lecturers who are negligent of their duties are reasonably punished as a deterrent to others (Mean = 2.22), lecturers are adequately rewarded for their commitment to duty through exceptional performance (Mean = 2.66), and lecturers are given facilities for recreation and relaxation so as to reduce their mental stress resulting from the complex activities of their office (Mean = 2.17) did not meet the threshold mark and thereby were considered as ineffective in the extent of application of McGregor's theory of Management in the area of study. Furthermore, the items are not accepted as effective in the extent of application of McGregor's theory in conflict resolutions in the area of study because of an overall Mean of 2.68 and Standard Deviation of 0.16 which did not meet the cut-off mark. It is thus concluded that the application of McGregor's Theory of Management is low and unsatisfactory in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Research Question Two:

RQ2: What is the extent of the application of Decision-Making in Tertiary Educational Institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria? The responses from the extent of the application of Decision making in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria is derived from items 1-8 of the Application of Decision-Making Techniques Questionnaire (ADMTQ), presented in the table 2

Table 2: Extent of the Application of Decision making in Tertiary Educational Institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	Std Dev.	Decision
1	Lecturers are familiar with the consensus techniques of decision making	2.16	.973	LE
2	Consensus techniques is commonly used in decision making in your institution	2.00	.748	LE
3	Consensus decision making is arrived at by the opinion of the majority even if disagree with minority or individual view	2.24	.622	LE
4	All group members are given the opportunity to contribute their ideas and suggestions	2.44	.791	LE
5	Each member avoids arguing rigidly for his own position to be adapted	1.95	1.261	VLE
6	Simplistic solutions such as flipping the coin are avoided	2.73	.971	LE
7	Members present opinions as objecting as possible for logical scrutiny and adoption	2.73	1.031	LE
8	Participant shape proposals into decision that meets the concerns of all group members	3.12	1.220	ME
Weighted Mean (\bar{x})		2.42	0.22	LE

Source: Field Work (2023)

N=333, Cut off Mean=3.00

KEY

VHE = very high extent -5.0, HE = high extent -4.0, ME = moderate extent -3.0, LE = low extent -2.0, VLE = very low extent -1.0

A look at table 2 indicates extent of the Application of Decision-Making in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. A look at the item on participant shape proposals into decision that meets the concerns of all group members (Mean = 3.12) is the only one that satisfied the threshold and thereby was considered as effective in the extent of application in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. But the table indicates that items on lecturers are familiar with the Consensus Techniques of Decision making (Mean = 2.16), Consensus Techniques of Decision making is commonly used in decision making in your institution (Mean = 2.00), Consensus Techniques of decision making is arrived at by the opinion of the majority even if disagree with minority or individual view (Mean = 2.24), all group members are given the opportunity to contribute their ideas and suggestions (Mean = 2.44), each member avoids arguing rigidly for his own position to be adapted (Mean = 1.95), simplistic solutions such as flipping the coin are avoided (Mean = 2.73), and members present opinions as objecting as possible for logical scrutiny and adoption (Mean = 2.73) did not meet the threshold mark and thereby were considered as ineffective in the extent of application of Consensus Technique of Decision-making in the area of study. Furthermore, the items are not accepted as effective in the extent of application of Consensus Technique of Decision making in the area of study because of an overall Mean of 2.42 and Standard Deviation of 0.22 which did not meet the cut-off mark. It is thus concluded that the extent of application of Consensus Technique of Decision making is very low and unsatisfactory in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Research Question 3:

RQ3: What is the level of effective conflict resolution in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria? This research question was answered and presented in table 3

The responses on the level of effective conflict resolutions in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria is presented in the table 3.

Table 3: What is the level of Effective conflict resolutions in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria

S/N	Item Statement	Rating	SD.	Level
1	The college management invites two conflicting groups for formal discursion in order to end disagreement	3.23	.936	ML
2	In using Dialogue each group is given the freedom of expression to the understanding of the other group	4.03	1.29	HL
3	In using Negotiation, Management ensures that each conflicting group is ready for give and take in this spirit of fairness	3.94	.523	ML
4	In the process of Mediation, Management tries to find things that everyone in both sides of conflicting can see as a middle ground to be agreed by all	4.23	.891	HL
5	In the application of conciliation, the Management tries to make angry people calm so that they can discuss or solve the problems successfully without violence	3.80	.871	ML
6	During Conciliation, Management tries to make angry people to be friendlier especially by being kind or giving something, they are fighting for.	3.37	.644	ML
7	The Management uses Arbitration by officially appointing somebody who is not involved to settle dispute when both sides agree to use a neutral person	3.89	.354	ML
8	The Management uses persuasion to settle disputes through convincing groups to agree to something by giving them good reasons for doing it.	3.53	.790	ML
9	The management sometimes uses command to instruct or give specific orders to conflicting groups to carry out some actions or desist from some actions as a way to resolve a conflict	4.30	.868	HL
10	Management permits conflicting groups to go to National Industrial court when it is unable to resolve matters to the satisfaction of the conflicting parties.	3.78	.642	ML
Weighted Mean (\bar{x})		3.81	0.26	ML

Source: Field Work (2024) N=333, **Rating Mean**=3.00

KEY:5.0 -VHL = Very High Level,4.0 -HL= High Level, 3.0-ML = Moderate Level, 2.0-LL= Low Level, 1.0-VLL = Very Low Level.

A look at Table 3 indicates Level of Effective Conflict Resolutions in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. A look at items on College Management invites two conflicting groups for formal discursion in order to end disagreement (Mean = 3.23), using Dialogue each group is given the freedom of expression to the understanding of the other group (Mean = 4.03), using Negotiation, Management ensures that each conflicting group is ready for give and take in this spirit of fairness (Mean = 3.94), the process of Mediation, Management tries to find things that everyone in both sides of conflicting can see as a middle ground to be agreed by all (Mean = 4.23), application of conciliation, the Management tries to make angry people calm so that they can discuss or solve the problems successfully without violence (Mean = 3.80), During Conciliation, Management tries to make angry people to be friendlier especially by being kind or giving something, they are fighting for (Mean = 3.37), Management uses Arbitration by officially appointing somebody who is not involved to settle dispute when both sides agree to use a neutral person (Mean = 3.89), Management uses persuasion to settle disputes through convincing groups to agree to something by giving them good reasons for doing it (Mean = 3.53), management sometimes uses command to instruct or give specific orders to conflicting groups to carry out some actions or desist from some actions as a way to resolve a conflict (Mean = 4.30), Management permits conflicting groups to go to National Industrial court when it is unable to resolve matters to the satisfaction of the conflicting parties (Mean = 3.78) satisfied the threshold and thereby were considered as effective in the level of conflict resolution. Furthermore, the items are accepted as effective in the level of conflict resolution in the area of study because of an overall Mean of 3.81 and Standard Deviation of 0.26 which meet the cut-off mark. It is thus concluded that level of the application of Conflict Resolution is moderate in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Testing

Three Hypothesis was tested in table 4 & 5

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between the application of management theories and effectiveness of conflict resolutions in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria.

This hypothesis was tested and presented in Table 4

Table 4: Relationship between Management Theory and Conflict Resolutions tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	r-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Mgt. Theory	333	18.74	2.186	.593	.000	H ₀ Rejected
Conflict Resolution	333	38.01	3.403			

Source: Field Work, (2024)

From the result of table 4, Management theories and Conflict Resolution were positively related and significant, $r(331) = .306$, $p < .05$. This indicates significant relationship between Management Theories and Conflict Resolution because the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance. Therefore, H_{0₁} which states that there is no significant relationship between Management theories and Conflict Resolution in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria was rejected. This means that correct application Management theories help in Conflict Resolution in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between the application of decision-making techniques and effectiveness of conflict resolutions in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria. This hypothesis was tested and presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Relationship between Fish Bowling Technique and Effectiveness of Conflict Resolutions in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	r-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Decision-making Technique	333	32.45	7.301	331	-.634	.000	H ₀ Rejected
Conflict Resolution	333	38.01	3.403				

Source: Field Work, (2024)

From the result of table 5, Decision-making technique and conflict resolution though negatively related were significant, $r(331) = -.634$, $p < .05$. This indicates significant relationship between decision-making technique and conflict resolutions because the p -value is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, H_{0₂} which states that there is no significant relationship between decision-making technique and effective conflict resolutions in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria was rejected.

H0₃: There is no significant relationship among Management Theory, Decision making Techniques and Conflict Resolution in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria. This hypothesis was tested by subjecting the Management Theory, Decision making Techniques and Conflict Resolution scores to regression analysis as shown in table 6

Table 6: Relationship among Management Theory, Decision Making Techniques and Conflict Resolution in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria.

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	SE	F	B	T	p-Value
Mgt. Theory	.648	.420	.418	2.596	239.434	.529	11.573	.000
Decision Making	.684	.467	.464	2.491	144.773	-.248	-5.431	.000

Dependent Variable: Conflict Resolution

Source: Field Work, (2024)

A look at the squared part correlations revealed that Management Theory accounted for 64.8% of the variance in job performance, $R^2_{adj} = .418$, $F(1, 331) = 239.434$, $p < .05$. It also reveals that Decision-making Technique accounted for 68.4% of the variance in Conflict Resolution, $R^2_{adj} = .464$, $F(2, 330) = 144.773$, $p < .05$. Thus, the significant results of the procedure indicated that the combination of the predictor variables were able to account for a significant amount of variance in the dependent variable.

This shows that both Management Theory and Decision-making Technique were an explanatory variable of Conflict Resolution, though analysis of regression coefficients indicated that Management Theory, $\beta = .529$, $t = 11.573$, $p < .05$ was more related to Conflict Resolution when the variables were in the model. This indicated that Management Theory was more related to Conflict Resolution. Therefore, H_0_3 is not accepted. Thus, it is concluded that relationship exists among Management Theory, Decision making Techniques and Conflict Resolution in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

The following are the major findings of the study:

1. It is thus concluded that the application of Management theory is low and unsatisfactory in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria.
2. The extent of application of Decision-Making Technique is very low and unsatisfactory in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria
3. The level of the application of Conflict Resolution is moderate in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria
4. Management Theory is more related to Conflict Resolution than Decision making Techniques in Tertiary educational Institutions of Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

This section discusses the findings of this study in relation to the findings of previous studies one after the other as follows:

The first finding showed that the application of Management theory is low and unsatisfactory in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. This finding is in line with Galani, & Galanakis, (2022). Conducted research on “A Systematic Literature Review on organizational Psychology on the Rise of McGregor’s X and Y Theory of management theory who found out that there is low and non-active involvement of putting into practice of the theory of X and Y. A number of recent studies were identified and concluded with ambiguous findings which later on lead to other studies in constructing a valid scale for evaluating X and Y attitudes-low behaviours and job performance. As well as the second findings show that applications of decision-making techniques are very low and unsatisfactory in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria as this is indicated in Table 2 of item no 5 where each member avoids arguing rigidly for his own position to be adapted with mean score of 1.95 rated below 2 thereby signifies a very low extent.

The third finding of the study indicates there is moderate significant level of relationship between both management theories and decision-making Technique and effectiveness of conflict resolution in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria as this is also in line with the findings of Adeyemi and Ademilun (2012), conducted research on conflict management strategies and administrative effectiveness in Nigeria Universities. who found out that there is a communication gap between management and workers and this were leading cause of conflict in the Universities.

While the fourth findings shows that both Management Theory and Decision-making Technique were an explanatory variable of Conflict Resolution, though analysis of regression coefficients indicated that Management Theory, $\beta = .529$, $t = 11.573$, $p < .05$ was more related to Conflict Resolution when the variables were in the model. This indicated that Management Theory was more related to Conflict Resolution. Therefore, H_0_3 is not accepted. Thus, it is concluded that relationship exists among Management Theory, Decision making Techniques and Conflict Resolution in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study investigated the application of management theory, decision-making techniques and effective Conflict Resolutions in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. The findings of this study have finally shown that application of management theories and decision-making techniques are related to conflict resolution. Therefore, both of the variable’s application of management theory and application of decision-making techniques in tertiary educational institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria needs to be improved to some high extent in order for the management to be more effective in resolving conflict to enable the carrying out of its administrative activities without having a disruptive environment.

Recommendations

1. The application of management theory and Decision-making Techniques should be encouraged due to the low and very low extent of application of these variables in the tertiary educational institution of Kebbi State, Nigeria.
2. Management because of the moderate level of effectiveness of conflict resolutions in the tertiary educational institution of Kebbi State, Nigeria, should give lecturers the freedom to express themselves by voicing out their concerns on issues affecting them without interference.
3. The management should ensure that justice prevails in treating disciplinary cases by the use of suitable technique like the Fish Bowling which is directly related to conflict resolution in terms settling dispute.

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